

EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL COMPONENTS AS PREDICTORS OF SCHOOL MANAGERS CORE LEADERSHIP AND CAPACITY-BUILDING PRACTICES

LEAND MARK B. DIOMAMPO¹

DELON A. CHING²

leandmark.diomampo@deped.gov.ph¹

delon.ching@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0001-7166-6027¹

0000-0003-1435-4371²

Sto. Niño Elementary School, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

Effective school leaders are thought to have a set of components, competencies, or constructs manifested by behavior that relates to effective or outstanding performance in a specific job or role. In lieu of this, this study aims to determine the significant relationship of school managers' emotional and social components to their core leadership and capacity-building practices. The researcher used Daniel Goleman's Emotional Intelligence Model with four domains: self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management. Among these underlying variables, the researcher limits the scope to 12: emotional self-awareness, emotional self-control, achievement orientation, positive outlook, adaptability, empathy, organizational awareness, influence, coach/mentor, conflict management, inspirational leadership, and teamwork. The use of descriptive and correlational research design-led in achieving the objectives of the study participated by 30 school managers and 111 teachers from the Schools Division of San Pablo City. The result showed that only emotional self-awareness was found significantly different among the emotional components. In terms of social components, social awareness as to empathy and all relationship management constructs were found significantly different. As laid out by the correlation between emotional and social components to the core leadership practices, a positive significant relationship was manifested. The same result was obtained between the correlation of emotional and social components to leadership capacity building. Multiple linear regression was conducted with the core leadership practice and leadership capacity-building on the emotional components. It was revealed that the coach/mentor, inspirational leadership, teamwork, and achievement orientation of social components in relationship management contributed significantly to the regression model. This suggests that for school managers and other aspiring leaders extremely practice and capacitate core leadership practices and capacity building, they should be highly competent with emotional and social components in terms of relationship management specifically being a coach/mentor, manifesting inspirational leadership, teamwork, and achievement orientation.

Keywords: Emotional and Social Components, Core Leadership Practices, Capacity-Building